

DIAGNOSTIC ALGORITHM FOR LARYNGEAL PATHOLOGY

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Introduction. The treatment of laryngeal diseases requires a multidisciplinary approach. However, choosing the right treatment strategy largely depends on an adequate diagnosis of all nuances of the disease. The similarity of the clinical and endoscopic presentation of laryngeal lesions does not always allow for a definitive diagnosis. In these cases, computed tomography (CT) of the larynx helps. However, it is difficult for clinicians to determine the appropriate CT examination option, including intravenous contrast enhancement, which necessitates the development of guidelines.

Objective: To develop an algorithm for CT diagnostics of pathological conditions of the larynx depending on the clinical situation. To develop an algorithm for CT diagnostics of pathological conditions of the throat depending on the clinical situation

Materials and methods. The study included 11 patients who were referred for hiatal CT with intravenous contrast after clinical examination and laryngoscopy, as well as 40 patients who did not undergo hiatal CT without intravenous contrast in 2019-2021. The main clinical reasons for AI's in-depth diagnosis were hoarseness or loss of voice (100%), dry mouth (70%), pain or a

feeling of coma in the throat (20%), and difficulty breathing (10%). Laryngoscopic signs were unilateral/asymmetrical changes (80%), impaired mobility of the palatine mucosa (60%), mucous membrane hyperplasia (20%), areas of hyperkeratosis (20%), pathological vessels (15%), the presence of areas inaccessible to examination (15%), and areas of stenosis that hinder examination (20%).

Results and discussion. We identified 4 categories of patients: 1) the primary cause of the changes in the throat, the diagnosis is unclear; 2) the primary cause of the changes in the throat, the diagnosis is clear; 3) the primary cause of the changes is not in the throat, the diagnosis is unclear; 4) The primary cause of the changes is not obvious, the diagnosis is clear.

In the first group (n=55), hipline CT with intravenous contrasting was required in all cases, even if contrasting was not initially planned. The most common pathology was hyperplastic larynx (p=30), however, the severity of changes did not allow for the exclusion of tumor damage. Thoracic contrast CT in this category of patients allowed to determine the areas of pathological contrast, from which the target biopsy was taken.

In the second group (n=55), the most frequent pathology was the cysts of the throat of various localizations (n=25). However, the absence of difficulties in establishing the diagnosis did not eliminate the need for CTgortany with intravenous contrasting of Al to clarify the details of the pathology. In the case of differential diagnosis between benign mycista formation (n=9) and the nature of contrast and the dynamics of contrast preparation accumulation on CT, the issues were resolved.

In the third group (n=10), the main reason for Al's pre-examination was the absence of structural changes according to laryngoscopy. In this category of patients, the diagnostic algorithm was completely changed after contrast-free throat CT: b patients were diagnosed with pulmonary tumors, and u2 patients with midsection tumors were diagnosed with tumors of the posterior cranial fossa.

In the fourth group (n=30), the main cause of the pre-examination AI was a stenosis of the throat, and in all cases, the diagnosis was known, and the patient was admitted to correct these changes. Thoracic CT without intravenous contrast in this category provided comprehensive information, based on which further treatment tactics were determined.

Conclusion. In our opinion, the first step is to conduct a clinical examination and laryngoscopy of all patients suspected of developing hiatal roof. This allows us to determine where the primary cause of the changes is located - in the throat or outside it. In case of impaired tracheal airway throughput (as a rule, this is indicated by the data of the medical history), the KT of the throat without contrast in most cases is sufficient to determine the exact location and severity of the changes.

We believe that using such an algorithm allows for the rational use of existing diagnostic resources and the resolution of most clinical situations.